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Prevalence Of Iliopsoas Muscle Tightness And Its Association With Low Back Pain In Salon Workers: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Cross-Sectional Study, **Background:** Salon employees devote a considerable amount of their Iliopsoas Tightness, Musculoskeletal, work hours to standing, bending and performing repetitive tasks. This Non-Specific Low Back Pain, Numeric can, however, lead to musculoskeletal disorders. **Objectives:** To Pain Rating Scale, Salon Workers determine the prevalence of iliopsoas tightness among Salon workers and to find the association of iliopsoas tightness with occupational tasks performed by salon workers and non-specific low back pain.

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Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study of salon worker was conducted in Faisalabad on 108 salon workers; they were enrolled in the study through convenient sampling technique. Female salon workers of age 20 to 35 years with minimum 2 years of experience and working daily at least 6 hours were included. Numeric pain rating scale was used to check intensity of low back pain. Modified Thomas Test was used to assess iliopsoas muscles tightness. SPSS version 22 was used to analyze the result.

Results: Mean age of the participants was (24.49±3.8), with most having 2–8 years of experience (mean: 6.28±4.09). Iliopsoas tightness was present in 46.3% workers most often bilaterally and more prevalent among the younger participants. 75% of the participants reported Non-specific low back pain. A statistically significant association was found between iliopsoas tightness and age ($p=0.022$) whereas no significant association was found with occupational tasks, working posture, years of experience, daily working hours, or nonspecific low back pain ($p>0.05$).

Conclusion: In conclusion Iliopsoas muscle tightness was found to be prevalent among salon employees, particularly among younger people but it was not associated with low back pain, occupational tasks, working hours, or posture.

INTRODUCTION:

The iliopsoas is a crucial muscle group that affects hip and spine movement since it is the only one in the body that is connected to the femur, pelvis, and spine.^[1] This muscle group serves as the main hip flexor. Since the iliopsoas plays a crucial role in daily activities, including sports, any impairments or issues related to this muscle can lead to significant limitation.^[2] Low back pain (LBP) is defined as discomfort, tense muscles, or soreness in the region between the bottom edge of the 12th rib and the lower gluteal folds, regardless of sciatica. Work-related low back pain (WRLBP) is a prevalent health issue that many individuals encounter at certain stage in their lives. It can lead to absenteeism from work and costs associated with occupational disability, creating a significant economic impact on people, families, communities, and nations entirety.^[3] Tightness in the lower Iliopsoas can cause discomfort, pain, and aching in the front of the hip socket. This tightness has been significantly linked to back pain.^[4] According to previous researches the prevalence of musculoskeletal problems related to hip or pelvic was 18 % and low back was 45% in salon workers.^[5] This muscle often becomes tight due to a sedentary lifestyle, which can limit the range of motion (ROM) and mobility in the joints, affect functional activities of daily living. These muscles are usually not stretched during routine tasks and get tightens.^[4]

Non-specific low back pain is defined as a symptom with an unknown cause, meaning we currently cannot reliably identify the underlying pathology. Nevertheless, various factors have been recognized as potential causes of the pain or as influences on its development and progression.^[6] The 21st century saw the birth of the beauty industry that transformed luxury service into a necessary part of personal care, and nowadays it attracts more. They encourage people to pursue cosmetology and hair dressing careers. While focusing on making their clients look beautiful, their own health is frequently compromised because of activities involve significant movements.^[7] Tasks like manicures, pedicures, facials, hairstyling, massages, threading, and waxing all require long time sitting and standing.^[8] Beauty salon workers who consistently stand for more than eight hours and twist or bend their backs forward or sideways during their job are susceptible to back and lower limb diseases.^[9] They also demand prolonged sitting, which can have a number of adverse health consequences. Sitting raises the risk of musculoskeletal disorders and cardiovascular problems, which can result in adaptive postural alterations that hurt.^[10]

The objectives of study were to observe the prevalence of iliopsoas muscle tightness among Salon workers, to evaluate the association of iliopsoas muscle tightness with non-specific low back pain and to determine the association of iliopsoas tightness with occupational tasks performed by salon workers. The job of salon workers, require them to stand for extended periods, bend, and maintain certain positions, which can create tension in their muscles. While previous research has indicated that individuals in these types of jobs often experience muscle tightness, there has been limited investigation into how widespread iliopsoas muscle tightness is among salon workers or what factors may heighten their risk. Given that this group may be more susceptible to tightness and back pain due to their work. The rationale of this research was to meet this gap by examining the prevalence of iliopsoas tightness in salon workers and its relationship to non-specific low back pain. This information could be valuable in developing strategies to safeguard their health and alleviate their discomfort.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and population

A cross-sectional study was conducted to determine the prevalence of iliopsoas muscle tightness and its association with low back pain among salon workers. The study was conducted in the saloons of Faisalabad. Approximately, it had taken 6 months duration to collect and analyze data. The targeted population included females working in salons. The study was conducted with the sample size of 108 salon workers. Sample size was calculated by using the following formula: $n = (Z_{1-\alpha/2})^2 P \times (1 - P) / d^2$. Z-score corresponding to the confidence level (1.96 for 95% confidence) and P: Expected prevalence (0.076 for 7.6%).^[11] Data from the participants was collected by using convenient sampling technique.

Selection Criteria

Total 130 salon workers were screened out of which 108 met our inclusion criteria. The target population was screened and selected according to the defined selection criteria. **Inclusion Criteria:** Female Gender, Age 20 to 35 years, Minimum two years of experience and daily working of at least 6 hours. **Exclusion Criteria:** History of Acute/infectious arthritis, Osteomyelitis, Multiple myeloma, Hypermobility joint, Spinal cord compression, Advance degenerative changes, Cauda equina syndrome, Disc herniation, Neurological deficit, Radiculopathy, tumor, Malignancies/Metastasis, Osteoporosis, joint ankylosis, Myelopathy, Rheumatoid arthritis, Progressive Rheumatologic disease and Participants not willing to give written consent.^[12]

Data collection procedure

The written consent was obtained from participants prior to their inclusion in the study. Before receiving consent forms, all participants were fully explained with the study goals and given the assurance that their data would be kept private. Participants were screened and demographic data and other baseline details were enlisted on a form. The Modified Thomas test was used to measure the length of the iliopsoas muscle. Participants were requested to sit at the edge of the plinth and roll back while posteriorly drawing both legs to the chest. The test limb was then lowered toward the floor so that it hung freely over the edge of the plinth, while the participant was instructed to hold the opposite hip in maximal flexion with their arms. The criterion for identifying iliopsoas muscle shortening was a 5 degree or greater hip joint extension deficit attributed to the iliopsoas.^[13] The Modified Thomas Test displayed a sensitivity of 31.82% and a specificity of 57.14%) for testing hip extension deficits.^[14] 11-point Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) was utilized to assess the patient's pain level. This scale is marked on the left with the term "no pain" and on the right with "worst imaginable pain." Patients are asked to evaluate their current pain level, as well as their highest and lowest pain experiences over the past 24 hours. The patient's pain level can be represented by the average of these three ratings or by any one of the individual ratings. Research has demonstrated that numeric pain scales are both reliable and valid. For test-retest reliability, the Intra class correlation coefficient values calculated from the stable patients was 74% for the NPRS.^[15]

Data analysis

Data analysis was done using the SPSS version 22.

Ethical Consideration

Study received ethical approval from the institution review board of "The University of Faisalabad". Participants were asked to sign written consent form. It was assured that information was only used for research purposes and they had given a description of the study before their consent is taken. Privacy and confidentiality of the patient was preserved. All information regarding the study was provided to the patients in an effective manner.

RESULTS

Demographic statistics

Age was categorized as 20-24 years, 25-29 years, 30-34 years. Figure 1 shows that 64 participants lied in 20 to 24 years category, while 30 participants lied in 25 to 29 years and 14 participants lied in 30 to 34 years. The average age of subject was 24.49 ± 3.8 . The key task of participant was categorized as hairdressing, make-up, skin care services, manicure pedicure. Figure 2 shows that 42 participants provide hairdressing services, 14 participants do make-up, 31 participants provide skin care services and 21 provide manicure pedicure services. Figure 3 shows that 84 participants worked in standing posture and 24 participants worked in sitting posture. Figure 4 shows that 58 participants worked 7-9 hours, while 50 participants worked 10-12 hours. The average daily working hours of participant were 9.4 ± 1.218 .

Figure 1: Age of participant

Figure 2: Key tasks

Figure 3: Everyday working posture

Figure 4: Working hours

Table 1: Frequency of iliopsoas muscle tightness

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Absent	58	53.7	53.7	53.7
	present	50	46.3	46.3	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

The table 1 reveals the presence of iliopsoas muscle tightness. It shows that in 58 salon workers iliopsoas muscle tightness was absent, while in 50 salon workers iliopsoas muscle tightness was present.

Table 2: Frequency of Non-specific low back pain in participants

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Absent	26	24.1	24.1	24.1
	Present	82	75.9	75.9	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

The table 2 reveals the presence of nonspecific low back pain .It shows that, in 26 participants' non-specific low back pain was absent; while in 82 participants' non- specific low back pain was present.

Table 3: Association of iliopsoas muscle tightness with demographics, occupational tasks and low back pain

Sr. No	Variable Associated With Iliopsoas Tightness	Test	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
1	Age	Pearson Chi-Square	7.616	2	0.022*
		Likelihood Ratio	7.730	2	0.021
		Linear-by-Linear Association	7.482	1	0.006
		N of Valid Cases			108
2	Key Tasks	Pearson Chi-Square	2.549	3	0.467
		Likelihood Ratio	2.561	3	0.464
		Linear-by-Linear Association	2.012	1	0.156
		N of Valid Cases			108
3	Everyday Task Postures	Pearson Chi-Square	0.769	1	0.381
		Continuity Correction	0.416	1	0.519
		Likelihood Ratio	0.767	1	0.381
		Linear-by-Linear Association	0.762	1	0.383
		N of Valid Cases			108
4	Years of Experience	Pearson Chi-Square	0.815	2	0.665
		Likelihood Ratio	0.814	2	0.666
		Linear-by-Linear Association	0.803	1	0.370
		N of Valid Cases			108
5	Average Daily Working Hours	Pearson Chi-Square	1.485	1	0.223
		Continuity Correction	1.050	1	0.305
		Likelihood Ratio	1.489	1	0.222
		Linear-by-Linear Association	1.471	1	0.225
		N of Valid Cases			108
6	Non-Specific Low Back Pain	Pearson Chi-Square	0.000	1	0.987
		Continuity Correction	0.000	1	1.000
		Likelihood Ratio	0.000	1	0.987
		Linear-by-Linear Association	0.000	1	0.987
		N of Valid Cases			108

* shows statistical significant association

Table 3 shows the association of iliopsoas muscle tightness with demographics, occupational tasks and low back pain. A statistical significant association was found between presence of iliopsoas muscle tightness and age of participants ($p < 0.05$). However no statistical significant association was found between occupational tasks, working postures, years of experience, daily working hours and non-specific low back pain.

DISCUSSION

The iliopsoas is a major muscle group which influences hip and spine movement since it is the only one in the body that is linked to the femur, pelvis, and spine. ^[1] The iliacus, psoas major, and psoas minor are the three muscles that make up the iliopsoas tendon muscle complex. ^[16] The primary hip flexor is this muscle group. The iliopsoas is an essential muscle for everyday activities, including sports, so any problems or impairments affecting it might result in serious limitations. ^[2] With or without sciatica, low back pain (LBP) is defined as pain, stiffness, or tightness in the muscles between the lower gluteal folds and the bottom edge of the 12th rib. ^[3] Tightness in the lower iliopsoas can lead to discomfort, pain, and a nagging ache in the front of the hip socket. When the iliopsoas group becomes shortened, it can pull the spine into hyperlordosis and tilt the pelvis forward, putting extra stress on all the spinal muscles, as well as the erector spinae. A muscle imbalance occurs when the length or strength of one muscle disrupts its own function or that of its

opposing muscle. For example, tightness in the iliopsoas can limit the range of motion during hip extension and impact the force production of the hip extensor muscles. a common health issues that many people face at any time in their life. ^[4]

The present study included 108 participants, primarily aged between 20 and 24 years (mean age: 24.49 ± 3.8), with most having 2–8 years of experience (mean: 6.28 ± 4.09). Key tasks performed included hairdressing (42 participants), skin care (31), manicure/pedicure (21), and make-up (14). A majority (84) worked in standing posture and 58 worked 7–9 hours daily, while 50 worked 10–12 hours (mean: 9.44 ± 1.22). Iliopsoas muscle tightness was present in 50 participants most commonly bilateral and more frequent in younger age groups. A shortened Iliopsoas group can also strain the erector spinae and other spinal muscles ^[4]. Due to its ability to pull and twist the vertebrae, a short Iliopsoas muscle may result in disc hernia and severe disc compression ^[4]. Lower back and sacroiliac joint pain and stiffness might result from iliopsoas dysfunction ^[4]. Right-side tightness was found in 41, and left-side in 35 participants. Non-specific low back pain was reported by 82 participants. However, our study unveiled a significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) between iliopsoas tightness and age, indicating that tightness may grow with age. Endo et al. also observed a similar pattern, noting higher positive Modified Thomas Test findings with age. Only a small percentage of our participants were older than twenty-four. The low prevalence of LBP in our sample could also be attributed to this age distribution. ^[17]

In terms of working conditions, the majority (84 out of 108) worked in standing positions, and 58 worked 7–9 hours per day, factors often associated with musculoskeletal strain. However, even among those with prolonged standing or long working hours, our findings did not show a consistent correlation between work conditions, iliopsoas tightness, and LBP. This mirrors findings from Kato et al., who concluded that neither iliopsoas nor hamstring tightness alone significantly predicted low back pain. In our study as well, despite 50 participants having tightness, 26 of them did not report any low back pain, further supporting Kato's conclusion. ^[18]

Although 74% of participants with iliopsoas muscle tension performed tasks in standing position, there was no statistically significant link between muscle tightness and occupational posture ($p = 0.467$). This shows that, whereas iliopsoas tightness is widespread among participants, occupational posture may not significantly predict or influence the occurrence of muscle tightness in statistical terms. Similarly, a study examining the impact of iliopsoas muscle length on lumbar spine postural and mobility characteristics discovered that as the iliopsoas muscle contracted, intervertebral mobility increased at the L1-L2 and T12-L1 segments, with a weak tendency towards increased lumbar lordosis. There was no link established between iliopsoas muscle length and lumbar extension range. Both studies found that, while iliopsoas muscle tightness can have local biomechanical effects, such as influencing segmental mobility and spinal curvature, these changes may not always translate into broader functional limitations or be significantly associated with occupational posture patterns. Thus, iliopsoas tightness may affect biomechanics, but it does not appear to independently predict low back pain in salon workers. ^[19]

Tightness in the iliopsoas muscle was not statistically associated with nonspecific low back pain ($p = 0.987$), average daily working hours ($p = 0.223$), or job posture ($p = 0.381$) among salon employees. Despite the fact that 50 participants had iliopsoas tightness, low back discomfort did not correlate with the distribution of working hours or standing or sitting postures. On the other hand, iliopsoas tightness was found to be significantly associated with lower hip extensor strength, restricted lumbar mobility, and extended sitting posture in a study by Ekbut W. et al. While both studies investigated work-related factors and iliopsoas involvement, the findings may differ due to each study's focus—this study emphasized the existence of pain, whereas Ekbut et al. assessed functional impairments. These opposing findings illustrate the complexities of factors impacting low back pain and the significance of context in interpreting muscle tightness findings. ^[20]

This shows that, while iliopsoas tightness was common, it may not be a standalone risk factor for developing low back discomfort. Low back pain is a multifaceted problem, and factors such as age, muscle strength, ergonomic habits, and psychosocial aspects may play a greater impact than isolated tightness in the

muscles.

Limitations:

Data collection was performed in only one city. Data was collected through convenient sampling technique. Only female workers were recruited in the study.

Recommendations:

Future studies are recommended with longitudinal study design. Future studies are recommended with targeting the other cities of Pakistan, with larger sample size and both genders. Interventional studies are recommended to be performed in future by targeting this specific population to address the iliopsoas muscle tightness.

Strength of study:

Measurement accuracy and consistency were ensured by the use of validated and trustworthy evaluation tools. Furthermore, the prevalence information gathered from this study can be used to create focused treatments for the targeted population that was identified.

CONCLUSION

In Conclusion, iliopsoas muscle tightness was found to be present among salon workers and its possible link to low back pain and workplace factors. The results showed that iliopsoas muscle tightness was present in almost half (46.3%) of the salon employees, with a moderate prevalence of bilateral tightness. Interestingly, younger participants were more likely to exhibit the tightness, suggesting that age may be more important than previously thought. The study found no statistically significant correlation between iliopsoas muscle tension and low back pain, despite the fact that 75% of individuals had low back pain, which was very common in this community. Furthermore, there was no discernible correlation between muscular stiffness and other aspects of the job, like years of experience, job role, posture, or daily working hours. The moderate but statistically significant relationship between age and iliopsoas muscle tightness indicates that, regardless of occupational exposure, tightness may progress develop or deteriorate with age.

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Authors Contributions:

AA, FQ, AN and KS contributed to conception and design. AA, FQ, AN contributed to data acquisition. AA, FQ, AN, IT and KS contributed to data analysis. KS contributed to article drafting and revising it critically for important intellectual content. All authors approved the version of manuscript to be published

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